

**MANAGEMENT APPRAISAL OF ROLE OF COLLEGES IN SHAPING THE PERSONALITY
OF THE STUDENTS
(Case study of Daund Taluka, Dist. Pune)**

Laxman Kisanrao Shitole

E. S. Divekar College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Varvand, Tal- Daund, Dist- Pune

Abstract:

Personality is what makes a person unique person and it is recognizable soon after birth. A second component of personality comes from adaptive patterns related to a child's specific environment. In today's world academic knowledge alone is not sufficient to grow and excel in life. A lot of other factors need to be taken care of before we go ahead. We see such things on a regular basis. Today it is no longer possible to get a job or an admission just on the basis of an entrance test. Each of these processes is followed by either a group discussion or a personal interview or both. This is clear that we not only have to be technically sound academically but also on other personality fronts.

For this purpose study area from Daund Taluka was identified. Questionnaire was administered for all the college students in Daund Taluka. The feedback received was analyzed with the tabulation and the percentages.

The establishment of new junior colleges in rural area, the strength of the girl's students has increased sizably. The performance of educational institutions in semi urban area are performing well as these are mainly privately owned institutions where the funds problem is not that severe compared to the educational institutions in the rural areas of Daund Taluka. The contribution of the educational institutions under the study area the researcher has observed that by and large their contribution in the personality development of the students is fair. The senior colleges are performing very well on the conduct of personality development programs for the students. Level of confidence level of sociability and level of self-sufficiency is higher in senior college students than junior college students. If possible both these sections may make agreements to show their students of appropriate class the Radio, Television program for their students. This will create interest in the minds of the students. The junior and senior colleges may be given grants for purchase of power generator of adequate capacity so that their laboratory work and other allied work which is dependent on power is not hampered.

The role of educational institutions in personality development is vital. The education is a behavioral science which is becoming more important in modern age. In today's world of knowledge industry, one cannot ignore the importance of education and thereby the personality growth of the students.

Accordingly, the educational institutions should undertake consistent research and extension activities in the area of personality development.

Key words: *Personality development, Group discussion, Personal Interview, Extracurricular activities.*

Introduction:

The term personality is open to many interpretations. Ordinarily personality is taken as the external appearance of the individual. Thus personality is not a static concept but dynamic one which is continuously changing due to interaction with the environment. Personality is known by the conduct, behavior, activities, movements and everything else show concerning the individual. Gordon Allport (1937) defines personality as "personality is the dynamic organization within the individual of those psycho-physical systems that determine his unique adjustment to his environment". White (1948) "Personality is an organization of

individual's personal pattern of tendencies".

Personality is what makes a person unique person and it is recognizable soon after birth. A second component of personality comes from adaptive patterns related to child's specific environment. The third component of personality is character- the set of emotional, cognitive and behavioral patterns learned from experiences that determines how a person thinks, feels and behaves.

Need to have good personality:

In today's world academic knowledge alone is not sufficient to grow and excel in life. A lot of other factors need to be taken care of before we go ahead. We see such things on regular basis. Today it is no longer possible to get a job or an admission just on the basis entrance test. Each of these processes is followed by either group discussion or a personal interview or both. This is clear that we not only have to technically sound academically but also on the other personality fronts.

Factors considered for good personality:

Personality cannot be broken up into distinct micro factors. Although a few of these can always be listed. These are; self awareness, general awareness, intelligent quotient, emotional quotient, social skills, presentation skills, creativity, communication skills, assertiveness, positive attitude etc. All these Factors and a few others can always be listed as a necessary part of the personality of an individual.

Techniques in handling people:

Don't criticize, condemn or complain, give honest and sincere appreciation, Arouse in the other person an eager want.

Six ways to make people like you:

1. Become genuinely interested in other people.
2. Smile.
3. Remember that a person's name is to that person sweetest and most important sound in any language.
4. Be a good listener and encourage others to talk about them.
5. Talk in terms of the other person's interest.
6. Make the other people feels important and do it sincerely.

Profile of college in Daund Taluka:

The below given tables give the data relating to colleges in Daund Taluka.

Research methodology:

A well designed questionnaire was prepared and administered to all the college students of all levels, the feedback received has been tabulated and percentage where workout. Daund town is the only semi-urban centre and the rest of the area is rural. Broadly it was observed that there is marked difference in semi-urban and rural areas and hence this segregation has been made. Ultimately this observation has been confirmed by this study.

Sr. No.	Type of Institution	2009-10			2015-16		
		Grantable	Non-Grantable	Total	Grantable	Non-Grantable	Total
1	Jr. Colleges	13	04	17	12	10	22
2	Sr. Colleges	02	03	05	04	02	06
3	PG Colleges	00	02	02	00	02	02
Total		15	09	24	16	14	30

Table No. 1- Number of Colleges in Daund Taluka during study period.

Year	From Daund Urban		From Daund Rural	
	No. of Junior Colleges	Total	No. of Junior Colleges	Total
2009-10	3	1942	12	3222
2010-11	4	2030	12	3429
2011-12	5	1863	14	2881
2012-13	6	1912	14	3105
2013-14	6	2226	14	3421
2014-15	7	2330	16	3670
2015-16	7	2387	17	4065

Table No. 2- Student strength of the Junior Colleges in Daund Taluka during study period.

Year	From Daund Urban		From Daund Rural	
	No. of Senior Colleges	Total	No. of Senior Colleges	Total
2009-10	2	1016	3	1202
2010-11	2	1017	3	1463
2011-12	2	1173	3	1588
2012-13	2	1194	3	1670
2013-14	2	1274	3	1622
2014-15	2	1267	4	1761
2015-16	2	1318	4	1710

Table No. 3- Student strength of the Senior Colleges in Daund Taluka during study period.

Year	From Daund Urban		From Daund Rural	
	No. of PG Colleges	Total	No. of PG Colleges	Total
2009-10	1	91	1	28
2010-11	1	145	1	24
2011-12	1	46	2	126
2012-13	1	178	2	119
2013-14	1	181	2	152
2014-15	1	225	2	157
2015-16	1	346	2	166

Table No. 4- Student strength of the Post Graduate (PG) Colleges in Daund Taluka during study period.

Level	From Daund Urban			From Daund Rural		
	A- Above 76%	B- Between 60 to 75%	C- Less than 59%	A- Above 76%	B- Between 60 to 75%	C- Less than 59%
Jr. College level	15	0	0	11	3	1
Sr. College level	15	0	0	11	3	1

Table No. 5- Data relating to efforts undertaken for personality development.

It is revealed that the efforts taken by the educational institutions at all levels in semi urban area are much more than the efforts taken by the rural area institutions. In the semi urban area i. e. educational institutions of all levels, the performance on this front is excellent and at rest of the Daund Taluka there is scope for improvement.

Level	From Daund Urban			From Daund Rural		
	A- Above 76%	B- Between 60 to 75%	C- Less than 59%	A- Above 76%	B- Between 60 to 75%	C- Less than 59%
Jr. College level	5	0	0	4	1	0
Sr. College level	4	1	0	3	1	0

Table No. 6- Data relating to availability of Infrastructure at various Educational Institutions.

Data relating to availability of infrastructure at college level is concerned by large group and same is the observation. At Daund 80% students have answered in affirmative securing “A” category, 20% students securing “B” category. Educational institutions of all levels are showing excellent performance in ensuring availability of the requisite infrastructure conducive for the development of the personality of the students. There is ample scope for improving the situations in the Daund rural area.

Level	From Daund Urban			From Daund Rural		
	A- Above 76%	B- Between 60 to 75%	C- Less than 59%	A- Above 76%	B- Between 60 to 75%	C- Less than 59%
Jr. College level	7	0	0	3	4	0
Sr. College level	7	0	0	2	4	1
Overall percentage of each rank	95.24	4.76	0	23.81	53.38	22.81

Table No. 7- Data relating to role of co-curricular activities and sports programs in mental and physical development.

Daund educational institutions have repeated their performance in securing “A” category, while in the rural area of Daund Taluka, there is needed to step up the efforts in this regards.

The performance of the educational institutions in semi urban area are performing well as these are mainly privately owned institutions where the funds problem is not that severe compared to the educational institutions in the rural area of Daund Taluka. The government should take a note of this situation and start funding the rural educational institutions at least in phase manner so that, these institutions will also fall with their counterparts in semi urban centers.

The infrastructure is available at all the institutions in Daund Taluka. As far as infrastructure relating to computer education is concerned, it has been observed by the researchers that, the government of Maharashtra has already provided computer support to the schools, which should be utilized for increasing the computer literacy.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Good (Less than 50%)	Better (50 to 75%)	Best (100%)	Total
		No. of Institutions	No. of Institutions	No. of Institutions	
1	Availability of Playground	10	3	2	15
2	Availability of Sport material	8	5	2	15
3	Availability of Library	10	4	1	15
4	Availability of Laboratory	8	4	3	15

Table No. 8- Performance of Educational institutions in Daund Taluka on infrastructure front as.

Observations and suggestions:

- ❖ Due to establishment of new junior College in rural area, strength of the girl students increased sizably. This is mainly because the junior College education has become within a reach. The general tendency observed in the rural areas is that they are not willing to depute their girl's students for College purpose at distant place. As these Colleges are nearby, naturally it provided opportunity to the girls students to continue their education beyond 10th standard.
- ❖ Keeping the clue from this observation the researcher is of the view that the government should encourage and UGC support whole heartedly for establishment of professional Colleges/ institutions at Taluka level and further it should provide ladies hostel at such centre's, so that the girls students from the rural areas may continue their further education.
- ❖ The contribution of the educational institutions under study area the researchers has observed that their contribution in the personality development of the students is fair. It has also been observed that, compared to the semi urban centre i. e. educational institutions at Daund in rest of the Daund the contribution of the educational institutions is marginally less.
- ❖ The senior Colleges are performing very well on the conduct personality development programs for the students.
- ❖ Senior Colleges for organizing several activities either the University or University Grant Commission provide some grant; as a result most of the Colleges are organizing various events which have direct bearing on the development of the personality of the students. Eg. Organization of various sport events, guest lectures, special program for communications/ soft skill development etc.

- ❖ In the rural area for developing personality in the students phase the infrastructure poses great problem. There are no private special classes for improving language skills, writing skills, audio-visual equipment for displaying the outstanding personalities and how those were developed etc. which are otherwise available at urban/ metropolitan centre's like Pune.
- ❖ The educational institutions at all levels should explore possibility of involving the parents in the various College programs. This rapport will also have positive impact on the overall College discipline and prosperity.
- ❖ Level confidence, level of sociability and level of self sufficiency is higher in Senior College student than Junior College students.
- ❖ In case of overall personality of the girls was found to be better than the boys.
- ❖ To tide over the current financial restraints the rural school in vicinity should come together and form a consortium, so that human resources as well as financial resources can be pulled together and on sharing basis the cost would come less. Each school may conduct one activity (say for instance: Elocution competitions, exhibitions etc.) and wherein the students from the consortium school may participate.
- ❖ Junior Colleges and Senior Colleges should as far as possible may make agreements to show their students of class the Radio, Television program for their students. This will create interest in the mind of the students.
- ❖ The government should established a scheme to train the potential trainers and give them professional training for personality development of the students. Three or four such professional teachers/ professors may cover Junior and Senior Colleges in their district and hold training camps for the students. Even if required a nominal fee may be collected from the students just to cover the out of pocket expenses for such a program.
- ❖ In every Junior and Senior College special efforts should be made to update the library and that the College authorities should take extra efforts to ensure that the students make use of the library.
- ❖ The Junior and Senior Colleges may be given grant for purchase of power generators of adequate capacity, so that their laboratory work and other allied work which is dependent on power is not hampered.

Conclusion:

With parents attaching more and more importance to quality education and with the middle class boom investment on school project is becoming a popularity decision. This has resulted in proliferation of schools. One very critical area is still not receiving the attention it deserves. This is personality development for children. With more and more competition to Medical and Engineering Colleges, the focus in higher classes is shifting to mark-scoring and not developing the personality. One important thing is the parent and teachers should not forget is the need for an all round development of personality.

The role of educational institutions in personality development is a vital role. The education is a behavioral science, which is becoming more important in modern age. In today's world of knowledge industry, one cannot ignore the importance of education and thereby the personality growth of the students. Accordingly, the educational institutions should undertake consistent research and extension activities in the area of personality development.

References:

- Allport G. W., (1937): "Personality, A Psychological Interpretation, New York, Holt.
Bhirud S. and Naphade B., (2008): "Principles and Practice of Management" Dimond Publications, Pune.

Chaube S. and Chaube A., (2008): “Philosophical and Social Foundations of Education” Vinod Pustak Mandir, Agra.

http://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Personality_development.

http://changingmind.org/explanations/personality/personality_is.htm